

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTION OF ASCOMYCETES ON THE TERRITORY OF THE KETMEN RIDGE (KAZAKHSTAN)

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Abstract

The mycobiota of the Ketmen ridge has 151 species belonging to Ascomycota. The ascomycetes are represented by 14 orders from 5 classes. The highest number of orders is characteristic of the class Sordariomycetes. The largest order is the order of Erysiphales from the class Leotiomycetes, with 38 species from 8 genera. The largest genera are *Erysiphe* (13 species), *Podosphaera* (9) and *Golovinomyces* (8). 13 genera have an unclear systematic position. Ascomycetes attack 183 species of vascular plants and mushrooms. The greatest number of species of ascomycetes (109 species) is noted in the steppe belt of the Ketmen ridge: on the northern macroslope 51 species from 44 genera, on the southern macroslope 42 species from 25. The following species are widely distributed in the territory of the study: *Erysiphe polygoni*, *Leveillula taurica*, *Neoerysiphe galeopsidis* and *Podosphaera aphanis*.

Keywords: coniferous forest, host plants, meadow, mycobiota, shrub belt, steppe belt

The Ketmen ridge is the easternmost of the northern chains of the Tien-Shan. The ridge is more than 300 km long, 40–50 km wide and 3500–4200 m high. The western part of the ridge (about 160 km long) is located on the territory of Kazakhstan, the eastern part – on the territory of China. The northern slopes are gentle, the southern slopes are steep, and the peaks are flat, not reaching the level of the snow line. The following types of relief are typical: high-mountainous steep (3000–3600 m), medium-mountainous (1900–3000 m), low-mountainous (1000–1900 m). Ketmen ridge refers to the Kungei-Terskei-Ketmen-South Dzhungar subprovince of the Dzungar-North Tien-Shan province (Akzhigitova et al. 2003). Due to the high aridity of the climate in the foothill deserts of Ketmen (altitude 1000–1200 m), ephemera and ephemeroids are practically absent. Above, within the limits of 1200–2000 m a.s.l., the steppe belt is located. On the northern slopes of the Ketmen ridge, the shrub belt (2000–2200 m) is well-developed. It consists of from a thicket of a dogrose, caragan, twig, cotoneaster, and barberry. In the bush belt there are separate fragments of deciduous forests. Deciduous forests are also characteristic of floodplains. At an altitude of 2200–3000 m a.s.l. there are coniferous forests from the Shrenk spruce, alternating with meadows, which is typical for the Tien Shan [1–3].

In mycological respect, the Ketmen ridge has not been studied for a long time. In 2004–2005 and in 2013–2017, an examination of the Ketmen ridge was carried

out. The gorges of the northern and southern macroslopes of the Ketmen ridge and the mountains Kuluktau, Karatau, Temirlik, Elshin Buyrik were surveyed.

Materials & Methods

The study was conducted in the Ketmen ridge (southeastern regions of Kazakhstan) for several years (2004, 2005, 2013–2017, 2021).

Different parts of plants with symptoms of fungal diseases and various substrates with visible fungal development were collected during field trips. A Canon 600E camera was used for photographing of fungi.

For light microscopy, small fragments of samples were stripped off the substrates, placed in a drop of distilled water on a microscope slide without any staining, examined and photographed using a photomicroscope Polyvar with Nomarski interference contrast optics [4]. Measurements of different fungal structure were made. Specimens were identified with the literature on Ascomycetes [5–13].

Dried specimens are stored in the herbarium of the Institute of Botany and Phytointroduction, Almaty, Kazakhstan (AA).

Results and Discussion

Checklist of ascomycetes from Ketmen ridge

The names of the host plants are given in accordance with the on-line identifier of plants [14], the names of fungal taxa – in accordance with the Index Fungorum database [15].

Ascomycota Caval.-Sm.**Insertae sedis**

Blastotrichum puccinioides Preuss. – on *Russula delica* Fr., near the village Tuyuk, spruce forest, 26.08.1971, N.M. Filimonova.

Fumago graminis (Corda) S. Hughes – on *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud., Ketmen gorge, 43°21'10.8"N, 79°44'16.4"E, 19.07.2015, G.A. Nam.

Fumago vagans Pers. – on *Berberis sphaerocarpa* Kar. & Kir., Ketmen gorge, 1503 m a.s.l., 43°21'10.8"N, 79°44'16.4"E, 26.04.2015, G.A. Nam.

Myxofusicoccum pyrinum (Kunze) Boerema – on *Armeniaca vulgaris* Lam., Avat gorge, 1733 m a.s.l., 43°19'00.6"N, 79°41'19.2"E, 25.04.2015, N Zhakhan.

Phragmotrichum chailletii Kunze – on *Picea schrenkiana* Fisch. & C.A. Mey., Avat gorge, 1673 m a.s.l., 43°19'13.0"N, 79°41'24.4"E, 17.07.2015, N Zhakhan.

Dothideomycetes O.E. Erikss.**Insertae sedis**

Asteromella acetosae (Sacc.) Ruszk. Mich. – on *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsk., Temirlik mountains, 1900 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, B.K. Kalymbetov.

Asteromella scabiosae (Kalymb.) Vanev & Aa – on *Scabiosa alpestris* Kar. et Kir., Temirlik mountains, 2200 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, B.K. Kalymbetov.

Botryosphaeriales C.L. Schoch**Insertae sedis**

Camarosporium caraganae P. Carst. – on *Caragana* sp., Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Botryosphaeriaceae Theiss. & Syd.

Dothiorella sibiraeae Murashk. & Sieling – on *Sibiraea tianschanica* Pojark., Temirlik mountains, 2700 m a.s.l., 03.08.1946, NI Rubtsov and EF Stepanova.

Phyllosticta acetosae Sacc. – on *Rumex tianschanicus* A. Los., Temirlik mountains, 1900 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Phyllosticta desertorum Sacc. – on *Astragalus petraeus* Kar. et Kir., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 21.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Phyllosticta ferruginea (Sacc.) Kalymb. – on *Artemisia dracunculus* L., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 21.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Phyllosticta lini Lobik. – on *Linum heterosepalum* Regel, Temirlik mountains, 2100 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Phyllosticta lycii Ell. & Kell. – on *Lycium depressum* Stocks., Temirlik mountains, 11.08.1937, M Popov.

Phyllosticta zahlbrückneri Bäuml. – on *Oberna wallichiana* (Klotzsch) Ikonn., Temirlik mountains, 2100 m a.s.l., 22.10.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Capnodiales Woron.**Davidiellaceae C.L. Schoch**

Cladosporium fasciculare Fr. – on *Allium* sp., Aktam gorge, 1469 m a.s.l., 43°22'42.2"N, 79°53'28.8"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova.

Cladosporium herbarum (Pers.) Link – on *Chrysomyxa deformans* (Dietel) Jacz. (III) on *Picea schrenkiana* Fisch. & C.A. Mey., Chakrambal gorge, 2284 m a.s.l., 43°07'63.7"N, 80°07'91.2"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Talas gorge, 2106 m a.s.l., 43°08'60.5"N, 79°47'37.7"E, 26.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Ulken Aksu gorge, 1500 m a.s.l., 43°20'07.1"N, 79°37'24.3"E, 04.08.2021, UK Jetigenova; on *Ziziphora clinopodioides* Lam., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 21.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Cladosporium olivaceum (Corda) Bonord. – on *Picea schrenkiana* Fisch. & C.A. Mey., Avat gorge, 1676 m a.s.l., 43°19'18.4"N, 79°41'24.8"E, 24.04.2015, UK Jetigenova; Ulkensai gorge, 1617 m a.s.l., 43°21'52.4"N, 79°57'02.6"E, 19.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva.

Mycosphaerellaceae Lindau

Cercospora depressa (Berk. & Broome) Vassiljevsky – on *Aegopodium podagraria* L., Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Fusicladiella melaena (Fuckel) S. Hughes – on *Doronicum oblongifolium* DC., south of the village Ketmen, 08.07.1957, VP Goloskokov.

Mycosphaerella tassiana (De Not.) Johanson – on *Calamagrostis epigeios* (L.) Roth., Ulken Aksu gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, LA Kyzmetova.

Ovularia epilobii Lindr. – on *Epilobium* sp., Temirlik mountains, 1600 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Ovularia schroeteri (J.G. Kühn) Sacc. – on *Alchemilla retropilosa* Juz., Temirlik mountains, 2200 m a.s.l., 25.06.1958, BK Kalymbetov.

Phacellium bulbigerum (Fuckel) U. Braun – on *Sanguisorba officinalis* L., Temirlik mountains, 2200 m a.s.l., 22.06.1958, BK Kalymbetov.

Phaeoramularia maculicola (Romell & Sacc.) B. Sutton – on *Populus talassica* Kom., Temirlik mountains, 24.09.1961, ZI Kubanskaya.

Polythrincium trifolii Kunze – on *Amoria repens* (L.) C. Presl, Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1703 m a.s.l., 43°07'40.2"N, 79°07'28.0"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan; Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Ramularia arvensis Sacc. – on *Potentilla impolita* Wahlenb., Kozhansai gorge, 13.08.1989, Ye Abenov.

Ramularia eremostachydis Zaprom. – on *Prunella vulgaris* L., Koksai gorge, 1925 m a.s.l., 43°22'57.3"N, 80°23'26.8"E, 01.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Ramularia gei (Ellis.) Linb. – on *Geum urbanum* L., Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Ramularia geranii (West.) Fuck. – on *Geranium collinum* Stephan ex Willd., Temirlik mountains, 1924.

Ramularia heraclei (Oudem.) Sacc. – on *Heracleum dissectum* Ledeb., Temirlik mountains, 24.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Ramularia medicaginis Bondartsev & Lebedeva – on *Medicago falcata* L., Saryzhaz valley, 2096 m a.s.l., 43°08'91.9"N, 79°58'25.1"E, 26.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova.

Ramularia pratensis Sacc. – on *Rumex* sp., Ketmen gorge, 1925 m a.s.l., 43°20'07.1"N, 79°37'24.3"E, 01.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Ramularia rufomaculans Peck. – on *Aconogonon alpinum* (All.) Schur, Temirlik mountains, 03.09.1959, LD Kazenas.

Ramularia rumicis Kalchbr. & Cooke – on *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsk., Aktas village, 22.06.1956, BK Kalymbetov.

Rhabdospora xylostei Lambotte & Fautrey – on *Lonicera* sp., Temirlik mountains, 2200 m a.s.l., 23.06.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Septoria aegopodii Desm. – on *Aegopodium alpestre* Ledeb., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Septoria alliicola Bäumler – on *Allium korolkowii* Regel, Temirlik mountains, 2200 m a.s.l., 14.08.1954, BK Kalymbetov.

Septoria alopecuri (P. Karst.) P. Syd. – on *Calamagrostis epigeios* (L.) Roth, Ulken Aksu gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, LA Kyzmetova.

Septoria erigerontis Peck – on *Erigeron aurantiacus* Regel, Temirlik mountains, 2500 m a.s.l., 05.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Septoria gentianae Thüm. – on *Gentiana* sp., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Septoria lycoctoni Speg. – on *Aconitum leucostomum* Worosch., Sulete gorge, 01.07.1960, YeI Andreyeva.

Septoria quevillensis Sacc. – on *Spiraea hypericifolia* L., Ketmen gorge, 2100 m a.s.l., 43°22'13.6"N, 80°20'56.5"E, 29.07.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Septoria senecionis-silvaticae P. Syd. – on *Senecio nemorensis* L., Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Sphaerulina berberidis (Niessl) Quaedvl., Verkley & Crous – on *Berberis sphaerocarpa* Kar. & Kir., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Stigmia carpophila (Lév.) M.B. Ellis – on *Armeniaca vulgaris* Lam., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, YV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1489 m a.s.l.,

43°15'44.3"N, 79°27'48.7"E, 16.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Kishi Aksu gorge, 1396 m a.s.l., 43°20'14.8"N, 79°34'02.9"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Dardamty gorge, 1369 m a.s.l., 43°23'55.8"N, 80°03'26.5"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova, Avat gorge, 1673 m a.s.l., 43°19'13.0"N, 79°41'24.4"E, 17.07.2015, N Zhakhan; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1703 m a.s.l., 43°07'40.2"N, 79°07'28.0"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Dothideales Lindau

Dothideaceae Chevall.

Scirrhia rimosa (Alb. & Schwein.) Fuckel – on *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud., Ulken Aksu gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, LA Kyzmetova; Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, YV Rakhimova.

Dothioraceae Theiss. & P. Syd.

Selenophoma rupicola Petr. – on *Tulipa* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1530 m a.s.l., 43°19'01.4"N, 79°30'06.4"E, 12.09.2014, ZhM Takiyeva.

Selenophoma sp. – on *Galatella punctata* (Waldst. & Kit.) Nees, Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1441 m a.s.l., 43°18'89.5"N, 79°29'85.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova.

Pleosporales Luttr. ex M.E. Barr

Cucurbitariaceae G. Winter

Cucurbitaria berberidis (Pers.) Gray. – on *Berberis sphaerocarpa* Kar. & Kir., Shoshanai gorge, 1685 m a.s.l., 43°11'08.6"N, 79°23'59.3"E, 11.09.2014, AK Dziyenbekov.

Cucurbitaria caraganae P. Karst. – on *Caragana frutex* (L.) K. Koch., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1536 m a.s.l., 43°19'51.6"N, 79°38'23.3"E, 24.04.2015, UK Jetigenova; Dardamty gorge, 1369 m a.s.l., 43°23'55.8"N, 80°03'26.5"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Caragana* sp., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1432 m a.s.l., 43°19'59.9"N, 79°37'29.6"E, 24.04.2015, ZhM Takiyeva.

Cucurbitaria pruni-avium Allesch. – on *Cerasus tianshanica* Pojark., Dardamty gorge, 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova.

Cucurbitaria rubefaciens Petr. – on *Salix* sp., Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova.

Didymellaceae Gruyter, Aveskamp & Verkley

Ascochyta kazachstanica (Byzova) Punith. – on *Ferula* sp., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, GA Nam.

Phoma eguttulata P. Karst. – on *Picea schrenkiana* Fisch. & C.A. Mey., Kaisysai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 24.08.1971, NM Filimonova.

Phoma festucina Thüm. – on *Festuca pratensis* Huds., Temirlik mountains, 1954, BK Kalymbetov.

Phoma graminis Westend. – on *Agropyron pectinatum* (M. Bieb.) P. Beauv., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 21.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Phoma xylostei Cooke & Harkn. – on *Lonicera altmannii* Regel & Schmalh., Temirlik mountains, 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Piggotia astroidea (Berk.) Berk. & Broome – on *Ulmus pumila* L., Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Leptosphaeriaceae M.E. Barr

Coniothyrium acantholimonis Kalymb. – on *Acantholimon alatavicum* Bunge, neighborhood Narynkol village, 14.07.1954, BK Kalymbetov.

Lophiostomataceae Sacc.

Lophiostoma vagans Fabre – on *Malus sieversii* (Ledeb.) M. Roem., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1605 m a.s.l., 43°18'07.8"N, 79°30'77.9"E, 12.09.2014, N Zhakhan.

Lophiostoma ephedrae Hollós – on *Ephedra equisetina* Bunge, Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova.

Phaeosphaeriaceae M.E. Barr

Ampelomyces quisqualis Ces. – on *Neoreysiphe galeopsidis* (DC.) U. Braun on *Marrubium vulgare* L., Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova.

Sphaerellopsis filum (Biv.) B. Sutton – on *Puccinia punctata* Link (II, III) on *Galium spurium* L., Akbet gorge, 1660 m a.s.l., 43°10'80.8"N, 79°13'54.4"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan.

Stagonospora atriplicis (Westend.) Lind – on *Krascheninnikovia ceratoides* (L.) Gueldenst., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 21.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Stagonospora fuckelii (Sacc.) Jørst. – on *Tussilago farfara* L., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, GA Nam.

Stagonospora vexatula (Sacc.) Sacc. – on *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1500 m a.s.l., 43°20'07.1"N, 79°37'24.3"E, 04.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Pleosporaceae Nitschke

Alternaria alternata (Fr.) Keissl. – on *Iris* sp., Kegen village, 1840 m a.s.l., 42°58'437"N, 79°22'405"E, 05.08.2012, UK Jetigenova.

Lewia scrophulariae (Desm.) M.E. Barr & E.G. Simmons – on *Kaschgaria brachanthemoides* (Winkl.) Poljak., Temirlik mountains, 11.08.1937, MG Popov.

Macrosporium meliloti Peck – on *Halimodendron halodendron* (Pall.) Voss, neighborhood Taskarasu village, 03.10.2004, LA Kyzmetova.

Pleospora loricina Rehm – on *Cotoneaster* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1667 m a.s.l., 43°17'83.7"N, 79°30'77.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova.

Pyrenophora pellita (Fr.) Sacc. – on *Nepeta kamirica* Regel, Temirlik mountains, 2100 m a.s.l., 22.06.1958, BK Kalymbetov.

Stemphylium botryosum Wallr. – on *Ferula* sp., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, GA Nam.

Stemphylium herbarum E.G. Simmons – on *Ferula* sp., Karatau mountains, 2020 m a.s.l., 43°02'22.6"N, 79°59'89.5"E, 25.08.2016, GA Nam.

Venturiaceae E. Müll. & Arx ex M.E. Barr

Lasiobotrys lonicerae (Fr.) Kunze – on *Lonicera stenantha* Pojark., Komirshi gorge, 2136 m a.s.l., 43°06'51.2"N, 79°37'54.9"E, 06.07.2017, YV Rakhimova.

Venturia inaequalis (Cooke) G. Winter – on *Malus sieversii* (Ledeb.) M. Roem., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1754 m a.s.l., 43°17'24.7"N, 79°30'50.5"E, 17.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; on *Malus* sp., Kyrgyzsai

gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Leotiomycetes O.E. Erikss. & Winka**Chaetomellales** Crous & Denman**Marthamycetaceae** Baral, Lantz, Hustad & Minter

Propolis farinosa (Pers.) Fr. – on *Lonicera* sp., Komirshi gorge, 2136 m a.s.l., 43°06'51.2"N, 79°37'54.9"E, 06.07.2017, EV Rakhimova.

Erysiphales H. Gwynne-Vaughan**Erysiphaceae** Tul. & C. Tul.

Blumeria graminis (DC.) Speer – on *Bromus squarrosus* L., Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°19'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Milium effusum* L., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Poa bulbosa* L., Ketmen gorge, 1503 m a.s.l., 43°21'10.8"N, 79°44'16.4"E, 26.04.2015, GA Nam; on *P. pratensis* L., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1531 m a.s.l., 43°19'36.9"N, 79°37'11.6"E, 13.09.2014, GA Nam; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Poa* sp., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1426 m a.s.l., 43°20'19.3"N, 79°37'28.4"E, 24.04.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; *ibid.*, 1489 m a.s.l., 43°19'46.8"N, 79°38'08.7"E, 24.04.2015, GA Nam; Ketmen gorge, 1535 m a.s.l., 43°20'53.4"N, 79°44'32.7"E, 26.04.2015, UK Jetigenova.

Erysiphe aquilegiae DC. – on *Aquilegia* sp., Zhulkungei gorge, 1885 m a.s.l., 43°21'13.0"N, 80°12'31.0"E, 21.07.2015, N Zhakhan; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Delphinium* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, GA Nam; on *Ranunculus* sp., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 2032 m a.s.l., 43°04'56.6"N, 78°53'11.5"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Thalictrum minus* L., Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1911 m a.s.l., 43°06'97.1"N, 79°16'23.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Thalictrum* sp., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, LA Kyzmetova.

Erysiphe astragali DC. – on *Astragalus* sp., Talas gorge, 2106 m a.s.l., 43°08'61.4"N, 79°47'34.3"E, 26.08.2016, GA Nam.

Erysiphe atraphaxis (Golovin) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Atraphaxis frutescens* (L.) K. Koch, Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova; on *A. pyrifolia* Bunge, Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Erysiphe berberidis DC. – on *Berberis sphaerocarpa* Kar. & Kir., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1685 m a.s.l., 43°11'08.6"N, 79°23'59.3"E, 11.09.2014, AK Dziyenbekov; *ibid.*, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1441 m a.s.l., 43°18'89.5"N, 79°29'85.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1635 m a.s.l., 43°97'40.0"N, 79°30'48.6"E, 17.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Aktam gorge, 1579 m a.s.l., 43°21'54.8"N, 79°53'33.6"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1500 m a.s.l., 43°22'30.7"N, 79°53'26.3"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Kishi Aksu gorge, 1463 m a.s.l., 43°19'38.6"N, 79°34'27.3"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1524 m a.s.l., 43°19'28.9"N, 79°34'30.2"E, 03.08.2021, UK Jetigenova; Akbet gorge, 1660 m a.s.l., 43°10'80.8"N, 79°13'54.4"E, 24.08.2016, GA Nam; Sumbe gorge, 1521 m a.s.l., 43°15'42.5"N, 79°27'40.3"E, 04.08.2021, UK Jetigenova; Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., N43°24'50.5", E80°03'43.6", 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova; on *Berberis* sp., Talas gorge, 2106 m a.s.l., 43°08'61.4"N, 79°47'34.3"E, 26.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova.

Erysiphe convolvuli DC. – on *Convolvulus arvensis* L., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *C. tragacanthoides* Turcz., Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Erysiphe cruciferarum (Opiz) L. Junell – on *Berteroa incana* (L.) DC., Aktam gorge, 1637 m a.s.l., 43°21'51.3"N, 79°53'32.0"E, 18.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; on *Camelina silvestris* (Maxim.) Korsh., Ulkensai gorge, 1617 m a.s.l., 43°21'52.4"N, 79°57'02.6"E, 19.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Aktam gorge, 19.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; on *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medikus, Ulkensai gorge, 1617 m a.s.l., 43°21'52.4"N, 79°57'02.6"E, 19.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Aktam gorge, 1579 m a.s.l., 43°21'54.8"N, 79°53'33.6"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Erysimum hieracifolium* L., Akbet gorge, 1664 m a.s.l., 43°10'81.9"N, 79°13'42.7"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Erysimum* sp., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Thlaspi arvense* L., Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Erysiphe friesii (Lév.) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Rhamnus songorica* Gontsch., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova.

Erysiphe hyperici (Wallr.) S. Blumer – on *Hypericum hirsutum* L., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 17.07.2015, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kuluktau mountains, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova

Erysiphe lonicerae DC. – on *Lonicera hispida* Pall. ex Roem. & Schult., Zhulkungei gorge, 1841 m a.s.l., 43°21'34.5"N, 80°12'34.2"E, 21.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva.

Erysiphe pisi DC. – on *Medicago falcata* L., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *M. lupulina* L., Kuluktau mountains, 1703 m a.s.l., 43°07'40.2"N, 79°07'28.0"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Vicia* sp., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Erysiphe polygoni DC. – on *Polygonum aviculare* L., Aktam gorge, 1579 m a.s.l., 43°21'54.8"N, 79°53'33.6"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Sumbe gorge, 1449 m a.s.l., 43°16'03.2"N, 79°27'36.7"E, 16.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kishi Aksu gorge, 1463 m a.s.l., 43°19'38.6"N, 79°34'27.3"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Karatau mountains, 2020 m a.s.l., 43°02'22.6"N, 79°59'89.5"E, 25.08.2016, GA Nam; *ibid.*, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, SB Nurashov; on *Rumex acetosa* L., Ulken Aksu gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, GA Nam; on *R. aquaticus* L., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., N43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *R. confertus* Willd., Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°19'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1660 m a.s.l., 43°10'80.8"N, 79°13'54.4"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, GA Nam; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Rumex* sp., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., N43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Erysiphe trifolii Grev. – on *Lathyrus pratensis* L., Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Trifolium pratense* L., Avat gorge, 1673 m a.s.l., 43°19'13.0"N, 79°41'24.4"E, 17.07.2015, N Zhakhan; Aktam gorge, 1637 m a.s.l., 43°21'51.3"N, 79°53'32.0"E, 18.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; *ibid.*, 1579

m a.s.l., 43°21'54.8"N, 79°53'33.6"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *T. repens* L., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, LA Kyzmetova.

Erysiphe urticae (Wallr.) S. Blumer – on *Urtica cannabina* L., Aktam gorge, 1637 m a.s.l., 43°21'51.3"N, 79°53'32.0"E, 18.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; *ibid.*, 1579 m a.s.l., 43°21'54.8"N, 79°53'33.6"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1617 m a.s.l., 43°21'52.4"N, 9°57'02.6"E, 19.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Shoshanai gorge, 1685 m a.s.l., 43°11'08.6"N, 79°23'59.3"E, 11.09.2014, AK Dzhiyenbekov; *ibid.*, 1421 m a.s.l., N43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; Ulken Aksu gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, GA Nam; *ibid.*, 1531 m a.s.l., 43°19'36.9"N, 79°37'11.6"E, 13.09.2014, GA Nam; *ibid.*, 609 m a.s.l., 43°18'70.9"N, 79°37'53.1"E, 03.08.2021, UK Jetigenova; Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova; Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°13'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, SB Nurashov.

Golovinomyces artemisiae (Grev.) V.P. Heluta – on *Artemisia absinthium* L., Karatau mountains, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *A. santolinifolia* Turcz. ex Besser., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *A. vulgaris* L., Zhulkungei gorge, 1841 m a.s.l., 43°21'34.5"N, 80°12'34.2"E, 21.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°13'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova, *ibid.*, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan.

Golovinomyces biocellatus (Ehrenb.) V.P. Heluta – on *Stachyopsis lamiflora* (Rupr.) M. Popov & Vved., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°13'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *S. oblongata* (Schrenk) M. Popov & Vved., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *S. ovata* Djugaeva, Kyrghyzsai gorge, 1667 m a.s.l., 43°17'83.7"N, 79°30'77.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova; on *Stachyopsis* sp., Kishi Aksu gorge, 1463 m a.s.l., 43°19'38.6"N, 79°34'27.3"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Stachys sylvatica* L., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1500 m a.s.l., 43°20'07.1"N, 79°37'24.3"E, 04.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Golovinomyces cichoracearum (DC.) V.P. Heluta – on *Cirsium* sp., Dardamty gorge, 1369 m a.s.l., 43°23'55.8"N, 80°03'26.5"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Galatella punctata* (Waldst. & Kit.) Nees, Karatau mountains, 2020 m a.s.l., 43°02'22.6"N, 79°59'89.5"E, 25.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *Hieracium* sp., Ketmen gorge, 1579 m a.s.l., 43°21'54.8"N,

79°53'33.6"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1637 m a.s.l., 43°21'51.3"N, 79°53'32.0"E, 18.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Serratula coronata* L., Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; on *Tanacetum vulgare* L., pass Ketmen, 1923 m a.s.l., 43°08'36.5"N, 79°11'55.4"E, 11.09.2021, EV Rakhimova; on *Tragopogon capitatus* S.A. Nikitin, Karatau mountains, 2020 m a.s.l., 43°02'22.6"N, 79°59'89.5"E, 25.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Tragopogon* sp., Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan; the Saryzhaz valley, 2096 m a.s.l., 43°08'91.9"N, 79°58'25.1"E, 26.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; on *Tripleurospermum perforatum* (Merat) M. Lainz, Ulkensai gorge, 1617 m a.s.l., 43°21'52.4"N, 79°57'02.6"E, 19.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva.

Golovinomyces cynoglossi (Wallr.) V.P. Heluta – on *Cynoglossum officinale* L., Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 2097 m a.s.l., 43°04'27.3"N, 78°52'21.15"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; the Saryzhaz valley, 2096 m a.s.l., 43°08'91.9"N, 79°58'25.1"E, 26.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; Chakrambal gorge, 2116 m a.s.l., 43°05'99.3"N, 80°03'72.8"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Lappula microcarpa* (Ledeb.) Gurke, Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Nonea caspica* (Willd.) G. Don, Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *Solenanthus circinnatus* Ledeb., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1500 m a.s.l., 43°20'07.1"N, 79°37'24.3"E, 04.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Golovinomyces hyoscyami (R.Y. Zheng & G.Q. Chen) V.P. Heluta – on *Hyoscyamus niger* L., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1650 m a.s.l., 43°18'99.3"N, 79°36'54.1"E, 13.09.2014, UK Jetigenova; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1703 m a.s.l., 43°07'40.2"N, 79°07'28.0"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova.

Golovinomyces magnicellulatus (U. Braun) V.P. Heluta – on *Polemonium caeruleum* L., Zhulkungei gorge, 1930 m a.s.l., 43°20'56.2"N, 80°12'39.8"E, 21.07.2015, EE Kurmantayeva.

Golovinomyces orontii (Castagne) V.P. Heluta – on *Papaver croceum* Ledeb., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1500 m a.s.l., 43°20'07.1"N, 79°37'24.3"E, 04.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Golovinomyces sordidus (L. Junell) V.P. Heluta – on *Plantago major* L., Chakrambal gorge, 2284 m a.s.l., 43°07'63.7"N, 80°07'91.2"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova.

Golovinomyces verbasci (Jacq.) V.P. Heluta – on *Verbascum phoeniceum* L., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1703 m a.s.l., 43°07'40.2"N, 79°07'28.0"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on V.

songaricum Schrenk, Sumbe gorge, 1477 m a.s.l., 43°16'07.1"N, 79°27'30.1"E, 16.07.2015, N Zhakhan; *ibid.*, 1475 m a.s.l., 43°15'48.4"N, 79°27'40.0"E, 16.07.2015, N Zhakhan; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1635 m a.s.l., 43°97'40.0"N, 79°30'48.6"E, 17.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., N43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Elshin-Buiryk mountains, 1953 m a.s.l., 43°00'78.1"N, 79°58'68.5"E, 25.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *V. thapsus* L., Ketmen gorge, 1925 m a.s.l., 43°20'07.1"N, 79°37'24.3"E, 01.08.2021, UK Jetigenova; on *Verbascum* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1667 m a.s.l., 43°17'83.7"N, 79°30'77.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova.

Leveillula duriaei (Lév.) U. Braun – on *Phlomis oreophila* (Kar. & Kir.) Adylov, Kamelin & Makhm., Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Karatau mountains, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, N Zhakhan

Leveillula taurica (Lév.) G. Arnaud – on *Artemisia dracunculoides* L., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; pass Ketmen, 1923 m a.s.l., 43°08'36.5"N, 79°11'55.4"E, 11.09.2021, EV Rakhimova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Clematis orientalis* L., Kishi Aksu gorge, 1396 m a.s.l., 43°20'14.8"N, 79°34'02.9"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *C. songarica* Bunge, Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°13'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Malva neglecta* Wallr., Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°13'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, SB Nurashov; on *Marrubium vulgare* L., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, GA Nam; Kishi Aksu gorge, 1524 m a.s.l., 43°19'28.9"N, 79°34'30.2"E, 03.08.2021, UK Jetigenova; on *Nepeta nuda* L., Sumbe gorge, 1477 m a.s.l., 43°16'07.1"N, 79°27'30.1"E, 16.07.2015, N Zhakhan; *ibid.*, 1475 m a.s.l., 43°15'48.4"N, 79°27'40.0"E, 16.07.2015, N Zhakhan; Ulkensai gorge, 1795 m a.s.l., 43°21'18.1"N, 79°56'34.0"E, 20.07.2015, EE Kurmantayeva; on *Onobrychis arenaria* (Kit.) DC., at the entrance to Tuyuk village, 1911 m a.s.l., 43°06'97.1"N, 79°16'23.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Peganum harmala* L., floodplain of Temirlik river, 1038 m a.s.l., 43°18'03.9"N, 79°11'70.7"E, 28.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov, Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°13'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *Scutellaria transiliensis* Juz., Kishi Aksu gorge, 1463 m a.s.l., 43°19'38.6"N, 79°34'27.3"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Vicia* sp., Ulkensai gorge, 1795 m a.s.l., 43°21'18.1"N, 79°56'34.0"E, 20.07.2015, EE Kurmantayeva.

Neoerysiphe galeopsidis (DC.) U. Braun – on *Dracocephalum integrifolium* Bunge, Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, N Zhakhan; Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, N Zhakhan; Akbet gorge, 1664 m a.s.l., 43°10'81.9"N, 79°13'42.7"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *Lamium*

album L., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Chakrambal gorge, 2284 m a.s.l., 43°07'63.7"N, 80°07'91.2"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Leonurus turkestanicus* V.I. Krecz. & Kuprian., Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1660 m a.s.l., 43°10'80.8"N, 79°13'54.4"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Nepeta nuda* L., Shoshanai gorge, 1685 m a.s.l., 43°11'08.6"N, 79°23'59.3"E, 11.09.2014, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Akbet gorge, 1664 m a.s.l., 43°10'81.9"N, 79°13'42.7"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Origanum vulgare* L., Sumbe gorge, 1475 m a.s.l., 43°15'48.4"N, 79°27'40.0"E, 16.07.2015, N Zhakhan; Zhulkungei gorge, 1841 m a.s.l., 43°21'34.5"N, 80°12'34.2"E, 21.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Baldyrgan gorge, 2078 m a.s.l., 43°05'09.2"N, 79°24'03.0"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Phlomis oreophila* (Kar. & Kir.) Adylov, Kamelin & Makhm., Zhulkungei gorge, 1977 m a.s.l., 43°20'39.9"N, 80°12'52.0"E, 21.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1841 m a.s.l., 43°21'34.5"N, 80°12'34.2"E, 21.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; Ulkensai gorge, 1795 m a.s.l., 43°21'18.1"N, 79°56'34.0"E, 20.07.2015, EE Kurmantayeva; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1703 m a.s.l., 43°07'40.2"N, 79°07'28.0"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; *ibid.*, 2078 m a.s.l., 43°05'09.2"N, 79°24'03.0"E, 27.08.2016, GA Nam; Chakrambal gorge, 2116 m a.s.l., 43°05'99.3"N, 80°03'72.8"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, SB Nurashov; Komirshi gorge, 2136 m a.s.l., 43°06'51.2"N, 79°37'54.9"E, 06.07.2017, EV Rakhimova; Karatau mountains, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, GA Nam; on *Prunella* sp., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, GA Nam.

Neoerysiphe galii (S. Blumer) U. Braun – on *Galium aparine* L., Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l.,

43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *G. spurium* L., Aktam gorge, 1637 m a.s.l., 43°21'51.3"N, 79°53'32.0"E, 18.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva.

Oidium sp. – on *Chelidonium majus* L., Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Phyllactinia guttata (Wallr.) Lév. – on *Cratageus* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1667 m a.s.l., 43°17'83.7"N, 79°30'77.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova.

Phyllactinia ribis (Jacq.) Z.Y. Zhao – on *Ribes* sp., Temirlik mountains, 20.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Podospaera aphanis (Wallr.) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Alchemilla cyrtopleura* Juz., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *A. xanthochlora* Rothm., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, LA Kyzmetova; on *Alchemilla* sp., Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1754 m a.s.l., 43°17'24.7"N, 79°30'50.5"E, 17.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; *ibid.*, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; *ibid.*, 1667 m a.s.l., 43°17'83.7"N, 79°30'77.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova; Ulken Aksu gorge, 1531 m a.s.l., 43°19'36.9"N, 79°37'11.6"E, 13.09.2014, GA Nam; Ulkensai gorge, 1795 m a.s.l., 43°21'18.1"N, 79°56'34.0"E, 20.07.2015, EE Kumantayeva; Aktam gorge, 1579 m a.s.l., 43°21'54.8"N, 79°53'33.6"E, 18.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Sumbe gorge, 1489 m a.s.l., 43°15'44.3"N, 79°27'48.7"E, 16.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Tattibulak gorge, 2027 m a.s.l., 43°24'42.3"N, 80°30'56.4"E, 31.07.2021, UK Jetigenova; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Chakrambal gorge, 2116 m a.s.l., 43°05'99.3"N, 80°03'72.8"E, 27.08.2016, GA Nam; *ibid.*, 2284 m a.s.l., 43°07'63.7"N, 80°07'91.2"E, 27.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; Baldyrgan gorge, 2078 m a.s.l., 43°05'09.2"N, 79°24'03.0"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Geum urbanum* L., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1703 m a.s.l., 43°07'40.2"N, 79°07'28.0"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Koksai gorge, 1925 m a.s.l., 43°22'57.3"N, 80°23'26.8"E, 01.08.2021, UK Jetigenova; on *Potentilla argentea* L., Zhulkungei gorge, 1977 m a.s.l., 43°20'39.9"N, 80°12'52.0"E, 21.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; Sumbe gorge, 1449 m a.s.l., 43°16'03.2"N, 79°27'36.7"E, 16.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva; on *P. bifurca* L., Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, GA Nam; on

P. pedata Willd. ex Hornem., Akbet gorge, 1664 m a.s.l., 43°10'81.9"N, 79°13'42.7"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Potentilla* sp., Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova.

Podospaera clandestina (Wallr.) Lév. – on *Sorbus tianschanica* Rupr., Temirlik mountains, 1900 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Podospaera dipsacacearum (Tul. & C. Tul.) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Scabiosa ochroleuca* L., Chakrambal gorge, 2116 m a.s.l., 43°05'99.3"N, 80°03'72.8"E, 27.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov; Karatau mountains, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, GA Nam.

Podospaera epilobii (Wallr.) de Bary – on *Epilobium hirsutum* L., Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; on *Epilobium palustre* L., Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, UK Jetigenova.

Podospaera ferruginea (Schldtl.) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Poterium sanguisorba* L., Kishi Shibut gorge, 2246 m a.s.l., 43°11'02.2"N, 79°53'35.2"E, 26.08.2016, UK Jetigenova.

Podospaera fugax (Penz. & Sacc.) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Geranium collinum* Stephan ex Willd., on *G. sylvaticum* L., Chakrambal gorge, 2284 m a.s.l., 43°07'63.7"N, 80°07'91.2"E, 27.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *Geranium* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Podospaera fusca (Fr.) U. Braun & Shishkoff – on *Taraxacum* sp., Ulken Aksu gorge, 1531 m a.s.l., 43°19'36.9"N, 79°37'11.6"E, 13.09.2014, GA Nam; Sumbe gorge, 1489 m a.s.l., 43°15'44.3"N, 79°27'48.7"E, 16.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1507 m a.s.l., 43°15'32.9"N, 79°27'57.0"E, 16.07.2015, EE Kurmantayeva; on *Valeriana officinalis* L., Komirshi gorge, 2136 m a.s.l., 43°06'51.2"N, 79°37'54.9"E, 06.07.2017, EV Rakhimova; on *Xanthium strumarium* L., floodplain of Temirlik river, 1038 m a.s.l., 43°18'03.9"N, 79°11'70.7"E, 28.08.2016, AK Dzhiyenbekov.

Podospaera leucotricha (Ellis et Everh.) E.S. Salmon – on *Malus sieversii* (Ledeb.) M. Roem, Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1667 m a.s.l., 43°17'83.7"N, 79°30'77.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova; Sumbe gorge, 1449 m a.s.l., 43°16'03.2"N, 79°27'36.7"E, 16.07.2015, ZhM Takiyeva.

Podospaera pannosa (Wallr.) de Bary – on *Rosa beggeriana* Schrenk, Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova; on *Rosa* sp., Karatau mountains, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, N Zhakhan.

Podospaera plantaginis (Castagne) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Plantago major* L., Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova.

Podospaera polemonii (L. Junell) U. Braun & S. Takam. – on *Polemonium caeruleum* L., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1817 m a.s.l., 43°07'13.2"N, 79°00'28.2"E, 24.08.2016, EV

Rakhimova; Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova.

Podosphaera tridactyla (Wallr.) de Bary – on *Cerasus* sp., Akbet gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°10'80.8"N, 79°13'54.4"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova.

Helotiales Nannf. ex Korf & Lizoň

Insertae sedis

Coniothecium cerasi McAlpine – on *Cerasus tianschanica* Pojark., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 21.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Cylindrosporium basiplanum Vassiljevsky – on *Spiraea hypericifolia* L., Kishi Aksu gorge, 1524 m a.s.l., 43°19'28.9"N, 79°34'30.2"E, 03.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Cylindrosporium pseudoplatani (Roberge ex Desm.) Died. – on *Acer semenovii* Regel & Herder, Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Cylindrosporium spiraeicola Ellis & Everh. – on *Spiraea hypericifolia* L., Aktam gorge, 1488 m a.s.l., 43°22'35.6"N, 79°53'27.1"E, 18.07.2015, N Zhakhan.

Diplocarpon mespili (Sorauer) B. Sutton – on *Cotoneaster melanocarpus* Fisch. ex Blytt., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, GA Nam; on *Cotoneaster* sp., Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Sorbus tianschanica* Rupr., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1688 m a.s.l., 43°17'36.4"N, 79°30'46.8"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, UK Jetigenova.

Diplocarpon rosae F.A. Wolf – on *Rosa* sp., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 01.10.2004, LA Kyzmetova; Shoshanai gorge, 1421 m a.s.l., 43°13'07.8"N, 79°21'57.7"E, 25.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kishi Aksu gorge, 1463 m a.s.l., 43°19'38.6"N, 79°34'27.3"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Dermateaceae Fr.

Pseudopeziza medicaginis (Lib.) Sacc. – on *Medicago falcata* L., Kuluktau mountains, Dalaity gorge, 1373 m a.s.l., 43°05'26.7"N, 78°53'53.1"E, 01.07.2016, EV Rakhimova; Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova.

Rhytismatales M.E. Barr ex Minter

Rhytismataceae Chevall.

Meloderma desmazieri (Duby) Darker – on *Juniperus sabina* L., Ulkensai gorge, 2000 m a.s.l., 30.09.2004, GA Nam.

Rhytisma loniceræ P. Henn. – on *Lonicera* sp., Koksai gorge, 1925 m a.s.l., 43°22'57.3"N, 00°23'26.8"E, 01.08.2021, UK Jetigenova.

Pezizomycetes O.E. Erikss. & Winka

Insertae Sedis

Torula antiqua Corda – on *Artemisia* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1441 m a.s.l., 43°18'89.5"N, 79°29'85.5"E, 12.09.2014, UK Jetigenova.

Torula splendens Cooke – on *Achnatherum splendens* (Trin.) Nevski, Elshin Buyrik mountains, 1953 m a.s.l., 43°00'78.1"N, 79°58'68.5"E, 25.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Lasiagrostis* sp., Ketmen gorge, 1453 m a.s.l., 43°21'50.0"N, 79°43'43.8"E, 25.04.2015, UK Jetigenova.

Sordariomycetes O.E. Erikss. & Winka

Insertae Sedis

Melomastia mastoidea (Fr.) J. Schröt. – on *Fraxinus sogdiana* Bunge, floodplain of Temirlik river, 27.09.1961, ZV Kubanskaya.

Strickeria artemisiae Lob. – on *Artemisia frigida* Willd., Temirlik mountains, 1700 m a.s.l., 21.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Strickeria atraphaxis Kravtzev – on *Atraphaxis frutescens* (L.) K. Koch, Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova; on *Atraphaxis* sp., Dardamty gorge, 1369 m a.s.l., 43°23'55.8"N, 80°03'26.5"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Strickeria ephedrae Golovin – on *Ephedra* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1476 m a.s.l., 43°19'96.9"N, 79°29'96.5"E, 12.09.2014, GA Nam; *ibid.*, 1530 m a.s.l., 43°19'01.4"N, 79°30'06.4"E, 12.09.2014, ZhM Takiyeva; Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Strickeria spiraeae Domaschova – on *Spiraea hypericifolia* L., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1530 m a.s.l., 43°19'01.4"N, 79°30'06.4"E, 12.09.2014, ZhM Takiyeva; *ibid.*, 1433 m a.s.l., 43°21'50.0"N, 79°43'43.8"E, 25.04.2015, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1536 m a.s.l., 43°19'51.6"N, 79°38'23.3"E, 24.04.2015, N Zhakhan; *ibid.*, 1462 m a.s.l., 43°21'50.0"N, 79°43'43.8"E, 26.04.2015, N Zhakhan.

Thyronectria berolinensis (Sacc.) Seaver – on *Ribes nigrum* L., Sumbe gorge, 1489 m a.s.l., 43°15'44.3"N, 79°27'48.7"E, 16.07.2015, UK Jetigenova.

Diaporthales Nannf.

Diaporthaceae Höhn. ex Wehm.

Phomopsis dipsaci (Cooke) Grove – on *Scabiosa alpestris* Kar. et Kir., Temirlik mountains, 2200 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Phomopsis loniceræ (Cooke) Grove – on *Lonicera microphylla* Willd. ex Schult., Avat gorge, 1445 m a.s.l., 43°21'47.6"N, 79°40'52.0"E, 25.04.2015, ZhM Takiyeva.

Hypocreales Lindau**Insertae Sedis**

Acremonium tulasnei G.R.W. Arnold – on *Lactarius deliciosus* (L.) Gray, pass Ketmen, 2000 m a.s.l., 24.08.1971, SM Lopychova, NM Filimonova.

Clavicipitaceae O.E. Erikss.

Claviceps purpurea (Fr.) Tul. – on *Agropyron cristatum* (L.) Gaertn., Baldyrgan gorge, 1997 m a.s.l., 43°04'98.7"N, 79°23'13.5"E, 27.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Akbet gorge, 1660 m a.s.l., 43°10'80.8"N, 79°13'54.4"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°19'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; *ibid.*, 1664 m a.s.l., 43°10'81.9"N, 79°13'42.7"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova; Karatau mountains, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, N Zhakhan; *ibid.*, 2020 m a.s.l., 43°02'22.6"N, 79°59'89.5"E, 25.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *Alopecurus pratensis* L., Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Dactylis glomerata* L., Akbet gorge, 1621 m a.s.l., 43°10'75.7"N, 79°19'24.9"E, 24.08.2016, N Zhakhan; on *Elytrigia repens* (L.) Nevski, Karatau mountains, 2061 m a.s.l., 43°03'75.0"N, 79°59'79.8"E, 25.08.2016, SB Nurashov; on *Leymus multicaulis* (Kar. & Kir.) Tzvelev, Akbet gorge, 1660 m a.s.l., 43°10'80.8"N, 79°13'54.4"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; *ibid.*, 1664 m a.s.l., 43°10'81.9"N, 79°13'42.7"E, 24.08.2016, LA Kyzmetova; on *Leymus paboanus* (Claus) Pilg., the Saryzhaz valley, 2096 m a.s.l., 43°08'91.9"N, 79°58'25.1"E, 26.08.2016, GA Nam.

Epichloe typhina (Pers.) Tul. & C. Tul. – on *Elytrigia repens* (L.) Nevski, Komirshi gorge, 2136 m a.s.l., 43°06'51.2"N, 79°37'54.9"E, 06.07.2017, EV Rakhimova.

Glomerellaceae Locq. ex Seifert et W. Gams

Colletotrichum graminicola (Ces.) G.W. Wilson – on *Leymus multicaulis* (Kar. & Kir.) Tzvelev, Temirlik mountains, 01.07.1954, BK Kalymbetov.

Colletotrichum liliacearum (Westend.) Duke – on *Allium* sp., Shoshanai gorge, 1576 m a.s.l., 43°11'41.6"N, 79°23'66.5"E, 28.08.2016, UK Jetigenova.

Vermicularia caricis Brunaud – on *Kobresia capilliformis* N.A. Ivanova, Temirlik mountains, 2200 m a.s.l., 22.09.1957, BK Kalymbetov.

Nectriaceae Tul. & C. Tul.

Nectria cinnabarina (Tode) Fr. – on *Rhamnus songorica* Gontsch., Dardamty gorge, 1369 m a.s.l., 43°23'55.8"N, 80°03'26.5"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; on *Ribes nigrum* L., Sumbe gorge, 1489 m a.s.l., 43°15'44.3"N, 79°27'48.7"E, 16.07.2015, UK Jetigenova; on *Ribes* sp., Ulkensai gorge, 1795 m a.s.l., 43°21'18.1"N, 79°56'34.0"E, 20.07.2015, EE Kurmantayeva.

Nectria phaeostoma Speg. – on *Caragana* sp., Dardamty gorge, 1369 m a.s.l., 43°23'55.8"N, 80°03'26.5"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Kishi Aksu gorge, 1463 m a.s.l., 43°19'38.6"N, 79°34'27.3"E, 28.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Phomatosporales Senan., Maharachch & K.D.

Hyde

Valsaceae Tul. & C. Tul.

Cytospora lonicerae Grove – on *Lonicera altmannii* Regel & Schmalh., Akbet gorge, 1613 m a.s.l., 43°10'74.9"N, 79°13'71.9"E, 24.08.2016, UK Jetigenova.

Cytospora microspora Rabenh. – on *Crataegus* sp., Dardamty gorge, 1443 m a.s.l., 43°24'50.5"N, 80°03'43.6"E, 26.08.2021, EV Rakhimova.

Cytospora salicis (Corda) Rabenh. – on *Salix* sp., Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Cytosporina flavovirens (Sacc.) Grove – on *Rhamnus songorica* Gontsch., Sumbe gorge, 1385 m a.s.l., 43°17'00.6"N, 79°27'06.0"E, 27.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Leucostoma auerswaldii (Nitschke) Höhn. – on *Malus* sp., Kyrgyzsai gorge, 1575 m a.s.l., 43°18'15.8"N, 79°30'44.4"E, 26.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Phyllachorales M.E. Barr**Phyllachoraceae** Theiss. & P. Syd.

Phyllachora graminis (Pers.) Fuckel – on *Leymus paboanus* (Claus) Pilg., Dardamty gorge, 1371 m a.s.l., 43°25'37.0"N, 80°04'23.7"E, 29.08.2016, EV Rakhimova.

Woronichina tranzschelii (Woron.) Naumov – on *Caragana aurantica* Koehne, Komirshi gorge, 2136 m a.s.l., 43°06'51.2"N, 79°37'54.9"E, 06.07.2017, EV Rakhimova.

Xylariales Nanf.**Xylariaceae** Tul. & C. Tul.

***Rosellinia* sp.** – on *Ribes nigrum* L., Avat gorge, 1733 m a.s.l., 43°19'00.6"N, 79°41'19.2"E, 25.04.2015, N Zhakhan.

Taphrinomycetes O.E. Erikss. & Winka**Taphrinales** Haeckel**Taphrinaceae** Gäum.

Lalaria tormentillae (Rostr. ex Sacc.) Kurtzman, Fell & Boekhout – on *Geum urbanum* L., Kuluktau mountains, Uzyn-Bulak gorge, 1723 m a.s.l., 43°07'21.0"N, 79°00'44.4"E, 24.08.2016, EV Rakhimova; Avat gorge, 1733 m a.s.l., 43°19'00.6"N, 79°41'19.2"E, 25.04.2015, N Zhakhan.

Recently, the mycobiota of the Ketmen ridge has 151 species belonging to Ascomycota (Table 1). The ascomycetes are represented by 14 orders from 5 classes. The highest number of orders is characteristic of the class Sordariomycetes. The largest order is the order of Erysiphales from the class Leotiomycetes, with 38 species from 8 genera. The largest genera are *Erysiphe* (13 species), *Podosphaera* (9 species) and *Golovinomyces* (8). Several genera (*Blastotrichum*, *Fumago*, *Myxofusicoccum*, *Phragmotrichum*, *Camarosporium*, *Coniothecium*, *Cylindrosporium*, *Diplocarpon*, *Torula*, *Melomastia*, *Strickeria*, *Thyronectria*, *Acremonium*) have an unclear systematic position.

Table 1

Taxonomic structure of the biota of ascomycetes of the Ketmen ridge			
Class	Order	Family	Genus (number of species)
			<i>Blastotrichum</i> (1)
	<i>Insertae sedis</i>		<i>Fumago</i> (2)
			<i>Myxofusicoccum</i> (1)
			<i>Phragmotrichum</i> (1)
	<i>Insertae sedis</i>		<i>Asteromella</i> (2)
		<i>Insertae sedis</i>	<i>Camarosporium</i> (1)
	Botryosphaeriales	Botryosphaeriaceae	<i>Dothiorella</i> (1)
			<i>Phyllosticta</i> (6)
		Davidiellaceae	<i>Cladosporium</i> (3)
			<i>Cercospora</i> (1)
			<i>Fusicladiella</i> (1)
			<i>Mycosphaerella</i> (1)
			<i>Ovularia</i> (2)
			<i>Phacellium</i> (1)
	Capnodiales	Mycosphaerellaceae	<i>Phaeoramularia</i> (1)
			<i>Polythrincium</i> (1)
			<i>Ramularia</i> (9)
			<i>Rhabdospora</i> (1)
			<i>Septoria</i> (8)
			<i>Sphaerulina</i> (1)
			<i>Stigmina</i> (1)
		Dothideaceae	<i>Scirrhia</i> (1)
Dothideomycetes	Dothideales	Dothioraceae	<i>Selenophoma</i> (2)
		Cucurbitariaceae	<i>Cucurbitaria</i> (4)
			<i>Ascochyta</i> (1)
		Didymellaceae	<i>Phoma</i> (4)
			<i>Piggotia</i> (1)
		Leptosphaeriaceae	<i>Coniothyrium</i> (1)
		Lophiostomataceae	<i>Lophiostoma</i> (2)
			<i>Ampelomyces</i> (1)
	Pleosporales	Phaeosphaeriaceae	<i>Sphaerellopsis</i> (1)
			<i>Stagonospora</i> (3)
			<i>Alternaria</i> (1)
			<i>Lewia</i> (1)
		Pleosporaceae	<i>Macrosporium</i> (1)
			<i>Pleospora</i> (1)
			<i>Pyrenophora</i> (1)
			<i>Stemphylium</i> (2)
		Venturiaceae	<i>Lasiobotrys</i> (1)
			<i>Venturia</i> (1)
	Chaetomellales	Marthamycetaceae	<i>Propolis</i> (1)
			<i>Blumeria</i> (1)
			<i>Erysiphe</i> (13)
			<i>Golovinomyces</i> (8)
			<i>Leveillula</i> (2)
Leotiomycetes	Erysiphales	Erysiphaceae	<i>Neoerysiphe</i> (2)
			<i>Oidium</i> (1)
			<i>Phyllactinia</i> (2)
			<i>Podosphaera</i> (9)
	Helotiales	<i>Insertae sedis</i>	<i>Coniothecium</i> (1)

			<i>Cylindrosporium</i> (3)
			<i>Diplocarpon</i> (2)
		Dermateaceae	<i>Pseudopeziza</i> (1)
	Rhytismatales	Rhytismataceae	<i>Meloderma</i> (1)
			<i>Rhytisma</i> (1)
Pezizomycetes		<i>Insertae Sedis</i>	<i>Torula</i> (2)
			<i>Melomastia</i> (1)
		<i>Insertae Sedis</i>	<i>Strickeria</i> (4)
			<i>Thyronectria</i> (1)
	Diaporthales	Diaporthaceae	<i>Phomopsis</i> (2)
		<i>Insertae Sedis</i>	<i>Acremonium</i> (1)
		Clavicipitaceae	<i>Claviceps</i> (1)
	Hypocreales		<i>Epichloe</i> (1)
		Glomerellaceae	<i>Colletotrichum</i> (2)
Sordariomycetes			<i>Vermicularia</i> (1)
		Nectriaceae	<i>Nectria</i> (2)
			<i>Cytospora</i> (3)
	Phomatosporales	Valsaceae	<i>Cytosporina</i> (1)
			<i>Leucostoma</i> (1)
			<i>Phyllachora</i> (1)
	Phyllachorales	Phyllachoraceae	<i>Woronichina</i> (1)
	Xylariales	Xylariaceae	<i>Rosellinia</i> (1)
Taphrinomycetes	Taphrinales	Taphrinaceae	<i>Lalaria</i> (1)
Total	14	24	73 (151)

The greatest number of species of Ascomycetes (109 species) is noted in the steppe belt of the Ketmen ridge: on the northern macroslope 51 species from 44 genera, on the southern macroslope 42 species from 25 genera (Table 2). The number of species of fungi decreases in the shrub belt and the belt of dark coniferous forests with meadows. In the bush belt there are 19 species of ascomycetes from 16 genera on the northern

macroslope, on the southern macroslope – 30 species from 19 genera. For the belt of dark coniferous forests with meadows, 5 species of fungi are characteristic on the northern macroslope; on the southern macroslope – 14 species from 11 genera (Table 2).

Table 2

Characteristics of Ascomycetes biota of the Ketmen ridge

Options	Northern macroslope			Southern macroslope		
	the steppe belt	the shrub belt	the dark coniferous forests with meadows	the steppe belt	the shrub belt	the dark coniferous forests with meadows
Number of species	51	19	5	42	30	14
Number of genera	44	16	4	25	19	11
Ratio of species and genera	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.7	1.6	1.3

It is interesting to note that in the steppe belt of Ketmen, many species of fungi (15 species) occur both on the northern and southern macroslopes. For the shrub and forest belts of the northern and southern macroslopes are characterized by different species of fungi.

Ascomycetes attack 183 species of vascular plants and mushrooms. The following species are widely distributed in the territory of the study: *Neoerysiphe galeopsidis* on representatives of the family *Lamiaceae*, *Podosphaera aphanis* on representatives of the family *Rosaceae*, *Erysiphe polygoni* on representatives

of the family *Polygonaceae*, *Leveillula taurica* on representatives of different families.

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